

Cation Mg-Dominated Coherent Phonon Transport Leads to Anomalous Thermal Conductivity in Mg_3Bi_2

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N-type $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb},\text{Bi})_2$ system has emerged as a groundbreaking thermoelectric (TE) material, renowned for its optimized electronic transport properties and intrinsically low lattice thermal conductivity (κ_l). However, the origin of anomalously low κ_l and its weak temperature scaling ($\kappa_l \sim T^{-0.5}$, deviating from the classical T^{-1} behavior) remain elusive. Employing a theoretical framework that integrates ab initio anharmonic lattice dynamics into a unified heat transport theory accounting for particle-like propagation (κ_p) and wave-like coherent (κ_c) transport, phonon renormalization, and fourth-order anharmonic phonon scattering, the thermal transport property of Mg_3Bi_2 is comprehensively investigated. It is found that the weakly bonded interlayer cation Mg atoms amplify phonon coherence through dynamic disorder, driving wave-like transport contributes $\approx 40\%$ to κ_l at 600 K, while four-phonon scattering significantly suppresses particle-like propagation ($>40\%$ reduction). The theoretical predictions of both the magnitude and temperature-dependent behavior of κ_l in Mg_3Bi_2 exhibit synergistic agreement with in-house and reported experimental values. This work pioneers key insights into the Mg cation sublattice tuning the particle-wave duality in phonon transport, its strong anharmonic potential disrupts phonon phase coherence while enhancing four-phonon scattering, collectively driving the low κ_l in Mg_3Bi_2 . This discovery provides two actionable design strategies—cation site engineering and coherent phonon tuning—for developing high- zT Mg_3Bi_2 -based thermoelectrics.

1. Introduction

Thermoelectric (TE) material plays a unique role in global sustainable energy solutions that benefit from its ability to achieve direct conversion between waste heat and electricity.^[1] However, the TE applications are severely limited by the low conversion efficiency,^[2] which is evaluated as the dimensionless figure of merit (zT) of TE materials. The expression for dimensionless figure of merit $zT = S^2\sigma T/\kappa_{\text{tot}}$, where S is the Seebeck coefficient, σ is the electrical conductivity, T is the Kelvin temperature and $\kappa_{\text{tot}} = \kappa_l + \kappa_e$ is the thermal conductivity consisting of lattice (κ_l) and electronic (κ_e) component, provides key insights into the criteria for maximizing zT .^[3,4] It should be noted that these parameters are inherently coupled and the lattice thermal conductivity κ_l is the only relatively independent parameter.^[4] As such, the study of κ_l has long been a research spotlight in the TE field.

Due to its intrinsically low thermal conductivity^[5,6] and excellent electronic properties, the *n*-type $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb},\text{Bi})_2$

system has emerged as a highly promising TE material in recent years.^[5,7–12] Moreover, the anomalous behavior such as the intrinsic low lattice thermal conductivity (κ_l) and the weak temperature-dependence observed in phonon transport of $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb},\text{Bi})_2$ system is of significant research interest.^[6,13–17] On one hand, compared with heavier ternary compounds (AMg_2X_2 , $A = \text{Ca}, \text{Yb}, \text{Eu}, \text{Sr}$; $X = \text{Sb}, \text{Bi}$), the binary $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Bi},\text{Sb})_2$ exhibits notably low κ_l ,^[6,13,18–20] indicating that the Mg at A site (cation Mg atoms, denoted as Mg_1) has an unexpected impact on phonon transport. Previous theoretical works concluded that the ultralow κ_l of Mg_3Sb_2 originated from the interlayer shearing transverse acoustic (TA) phonon modes and strong anharmonic mid-frequency optical phonons.^[6,13,16] Peng et al.^[6] predicted that the small ionic radius of Mg_1 induces unstable lattice site in the octahedral and thus resulting strongly localized phonon scatterings in Mg_3Sb_2 . Zhang et al.^[13] further demonstrated that the structure distortion originate from the relatively weaker Mg_1 –Sb bond and larger void space by the relatively larger atomic displacement parameter and flatter potential energy landscape of Mg_1 compared to those of Mg_2 in Mg_3Sb_2 . In addition, experimental measurement observed the feature of soften TA phonon modes especially for

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those along Γ -M, Γ -A, and Γ -L in the Brillouin zone (BZ), verifying its intrinsically strong anharmonicity.^[15,18] Furthermore, Yao et al.^[21] quantitatively analyzed the phonon scattering along the in-plane (Γ -M) and out-of-plane (Γ -A) directions in Mg_3Sb_2 , in which they find that not only the weak Mg_1 -Sb interaction in the distorted Mg -Sb octahedron but also the long-range Sb-Sb interaction contributes to the softening of TA branches. In conclusion, although the weakly bonded Mg_1 interactions have raised the attention, these studies^[6,13,16] attribute the origin of low κ_1 of $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb,Bi})_2$ system to the combination of low-frequency acoustic phonons (but it is dominated by Sb(Bi) atoms vibrations) and strong anharmonicity (but just considering third-order anharmonicity).

On the other hand, several works show that κ_1 of this system has weak temperature-dependence scaling, strongly deviating from classical $\kappa \sim T^{-1}$ behavior.^[14,22] For example, the experimental κ_1 of pristine Mg_3Sb_2 has $T^{-0.6} \sim T^{-0.9}$ ^[14] while the pristine Mg_3Bi_2 remain elusive.^[22] Zhu et al.^[14] found that the fourth-order anharmonicity was significant and phonon renormalization played a significant role in the weak temperature-dependence of κ_1 in Mg_3Sb_2 . They attributed this behavior to the asymmetric displacements of intralayer Mg_2 atoms, contradicting previous findings that Mg_1 atoms contribute to the strong anharmonicity. Yu et al.^[17] considered four-phonon interaction processes and phonon renormalization, a preliminary numerical agreement between experimental and theoretical values has been achieved in Mg_3Sb_2 , but the underlying mechanism of the weak temperature dependence has not been explained. In general, the weak temperature-dependence of κ_1 implies a thermal transport phenomena that observed in glass. Unlike crystals, non-crystal-like materials such as amorphous solids, glasses or liquids, transport heat via the coupling of localized vibrations, carriers exhibit wave-like behavior and diffuse through Zener-like tunneling mechanism between such quasi-degenerate vibrational eigenstates particularly. Different from the particle-like discussed by Peierls's semiclassical picture, the wave-like transport is related to the wave-like tunnelling and loss of coherence between different vibrational eigenstates.^[23] When the frequencies of the two modes ω_q^s and ω_q^f are closer, the wave coherence ($c/(\omega_q^s - \omega_q^f)$, where c is the speed of sound) increases, resulting in stronger tunneling.^[24] In fact, the weak temperature-dependence of κ_1 in the $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb,Bi})_2$ system could arise from the existence of wave-like contribution due to phonon coherence effects. Unfortunately, the underlying mechanism of the temperature-dependent trend and a comprehensive analysis of the effect of phonon renormalization, higher-order scatterings, and phonon coherent interactions on κ_1 in Mg_3Bi_2 remain elusive.

In this work, we employ Mg_3Bi_2 as a paradigmatic example to unveil the role of cation Mg atoms in governing the anomalous phonon thermal transport of $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb,Bi})_2$ system using a first-principles-derived unified framework. Beyond the traditional three-phonon particle-like thermal transport (κ_p) based on Boltzmann transport equation (3ph-BTE) in which the interatomic forceconstants are calculated at ground state (0 K, G-IFCs), we systematically incorporate phonon renormalization, high-order phonon scatterings and identify a substantial wave-like contribution (κ_c). Our calculations quantitatively reproduce both the magnitude and temperature dependence of κ_1 , achiev-

ing remarkably well consistency with experimental data. The emergent dual-channel thermal transport mechanism (synergistically combining particle-like phonon propagation and wave-like phonon diffusion) along with critical higher-order anharmonicity, are collectively used to underpin the anomalous feature of κ_1 . Crucially, the observed weak temperature-dependence stems from thermally activated coherent phonon diffusions that progressively intensify the wave-like channel. Pioneering atomic-scale analysis elucidates that the cation Mg atoms govern the significant wave-like contribution to phonon thermal transport in Mg_3Bi_2 . This study establishes a groundbreaking paradigm for TE materials design by unifying dual-channel phonon physics with phonon renormalization and high-order scatterings, providing not only a universal interpretation framework for Mg-Sb-Bi system but also comprehensive and actionable strategies for targeted thermal conductivity engineering.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Atomic Bonding and Lattice Thermal Conductivity

Similar as other layered 1-2-2 Zintl phases, the structure of Mg_3Bi_2 compound consists of alternately stacked 2D $[\text{Mg}_2\text{Bi}_2]^{2-}$ slabs and $[\text{Mg}_1]^{2+}$ monolayers with space group of $P3m1$. As shown in **Figure 1a**, the $[\text{Mg}_2\text{Bi}_2]^{2-}$ slab contains two equivalent Mg_2 atoms and two equivalent Bi atoms, while the Mg_2 atom forms a tetrahedra with four nearest neighboring Bi atoms. The Mg_1 atom octahedrally donates electrons to neighboring Bi atoms for the sake of charge balance, equivalently completing charge transfer from cation to the polyanions. After structure optimization, the lattice constants of Mg_3Bi_2 are $a = 4.83 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 7.11 \text{ \AA}$, which agree well with the experimental values ($a = 4.65 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 7.38 \text{ \AA}$ ^[25]) within 4%. The coordination environments of Mg atoms at different sites with their nearest neighboring atoms are presented in **Figure 1b**. In advance, we calculated the electron localization function (ELF) with isosurface level of 0.7 at (1 1 0) lattice plane (see **Figure 1(b)**), in which we observed that the electron charge transfer around Mg_1 atoms is less than that of Mg_2 . Furthermore, we computed the negative integrated crystal orbital Hamiltonian population (-ICOHP) of different bonds in Mg_3Bi_2 , which can generally be used to quantitatively analyze covalency and strength of the bonds. As shown in **Figure 1c**, the Mg_1 -Bi and Mg_2 -Bi bonding states dominate the occupied part of the -COHP spectrum. The -ICOHP value at Fermi level for Mg_2 -Bi bond is larger than that of Mg_1 -Bi bond, indicating stronger bonding for Mg_2 -Bi. This is consistent with the results of the layered crystal structure and the characteristics of ELF, indicating that the Mg_1 atom should experience weaker restraining forces and thus leading to strong anharmonicity accompanying with low κ_1 .

Therefore, we computed and measured the κ_1 of Mg_3Bi_2 compound as shown in **Figure 1c** in which previous reported data are also presented for comparison.^[5,18,22] The experimental results are reproducible. And the experimental data from both polycrystalline and single-crystal samples exhibit similar values and a weak temperature dependence, which is clearer in **Figure S1** (Supporting Information). Compared to experimental data, Ding et al.^[18] obtained an overestimation of κ_1 by using the traditional 3ph-BTE model with IFCs only at 300 K. If we further include

Figure 1. a) Crystal structure of Mg_3Bi_2 . b) Two kinds of atomic coordination environment of Mg-Bi bond in Mg_3Bi_2 , in which the electron localization function (ELF) with isosurface level = 0.7 at (1 1 0) plane in unit cell is presented. c) Comparison of negative integrated crystal orbital Hamiltonian population (-ICOHP) between Mg_1 -Bi and Mg_2 -Bi bonds. d) Comparison of computed average κ_1 with experiment data. Our in-house and reported measurements^[6,18,22] are based on polycrystalline and single crystal. e) Comparison of computed T -dependent phonon dispersion with experimental data^[15,18] of Mg_3Bi_2 .

four-phonon (4ph) scatterings with G-IFCs, κ_1 presents a significant reduction and finally leads to an underestimation. To accurately predict the κ_1 , we here developed the most advanced theoretical prediction model which includes the effects of phonon renormalization, temperature-dependent interatomic force constants (T -IFCs), and wave-like phonon coherent contributions to predict the κ_1 of Mg_3Bi_2 , and finally giving an excellent agreement with the measurements from both magnitude and temperature-dependence trend. In details, the weak temperature-dependence of $\kappa_1 \sim T^{-0.5}$ observed in measurements is well reproduced after considering wave-like behavior of phonons on the basis of considering both three- and four-phonon (3+4 ph) interaction with T -IFCs as shown in Figure 1d. This result suggests that the lattice vibrations of Mg_3Bi_2 are significantly influenced by higher-order scattering, temperature effects, and wave-like coherence.

2.2. Phonon Renormalization and Particle-Wave Duality

Figure 1e shows the temperature-dependent phonon dispersion, in which we can observe a significant frequency shift (phonon renormalization) due to temperature effects. To comprehensively understand the phonon behavior, we divided the phonons into low- ($\omega < 2.5$ THz), mid- ($\omega \approx 2.5$ -4.2 THz), and high-frequency ($\omega > 4.2$ THz) regions based on the phonon band gap. In details, the low-frequency acoustic phonons ($\omega < 1.2$ THz) exhibit a slight

hardening feature with increasing temperature, while the mid- and high-frequency optical branches show a significant softening accompanied by a narrowing phononic bandgap as temperature rises. The temperature-induced phonon renormalization is more prominent in the optical branches of the higher frequency region which is mainly induced by the weak Mg_1 -Bi bond (see the phonon density of states (DOS) in Figure S2, Supporting Information). In particular, we note that the acoustic branches along the Γ -M direction display a flatten dispersion and are essentially unaffected by phonon renormalization, which is consistent with reported observations.^[6,13,15,18] The flatten acoustic phonon bands is beneficial for sustaining phonon-phonon scattering of particle-like propagation. Correspondingly, the optical branch exhibits a pronounced flattening trend with reduced separation from adjacent branches, which facilitates wave-like coherent phonon tunneling effects. Furthermore, our observed phenomena are consistent with reported experimental data,^[15,18] see Figure 1e.

To quantitatively analyze the phonon particle-wave duality in Mg_3Bi_2 . We classify the phonons into three regimes according to their lifetimes (τ) based on the Ioffe-Regel limit (in time, $\tau_{\text{Ioffe-Regel}} = 1/\omega$) and the Wigner limit ($\tau_{\text{Wigner}} = 1/\Delta\omega_{\text{ave}}$, where $\Delta\omega_{\text{ave}} = \omega_{\text{max}}/3N_a$, ω_{max} is the maximum phonon frequency, and N_a is the number of atoms in the unit cell), as shown in Figure 2a. At 300 K, most phonons with $\tau > 1/\Delta\omega_{\text{ave}}$ locate at low-frequency region ($\omega < 2.5$ THz), which behave as the particle-like phonon

Figure 2. a) The phonon frequency-dependent phonon lifetime (τ) at 300 K. The blue stars and pink circles indicate the calculation with 3ph and 3+4ph, respectively. The Ioffe-Regel (in time) and Wigner limits are shown. b) Same as (a) but for mean free path (MFP) of Mg_3Bi_2 . The Ioffe-Regel limit (in space) is shown.

propagation and thus dominantly contributing to κ_p . However, in mid- and high-frequency regions, the largest number of phonons are in the intermediate region between the Wigner limit and the Ioffe-Regel limit, where the heat mainly diffuses in a wave-like manner with the major contribution to κ_c . We note that the majority of phonons are above the Ioffe-Regel limit and still exhibit the well-defined quasi-particle excitations. However, even at the relatively low temperature of 300 K, a considerable number of phonons remain below the Ioffe-Regel limit and still exhibit the liquid-like features. This suggests that the quasiparticle excitation of Mg_3Bi_2 exhibits liquid-like characteristics, contributing to the low dual-channel thermal conductivity. Similarly, Figure 2b shows a phonon population with mean free paths (MFP) shorter than the Ioffe-Regel limit (i.e., less than the interatomic spacing), indicating their contribution to wave-like transport. In addition, it can be observed that after considering higher-order scattering, the phonon scattering relaxation time is significantly reduced. Comparatively, the effect of four-phonon scattering is particularly pronounced for low-frequency particle-like propagation, while its impact on wave-like scattering appears to be relatively minor.

2.3. Role of Cation Mg in Particle-Like and Wave-Like Thermal Transport

To get more insights into the role of phonons in particle-like and wave-like thermal transport in Mg_3Bi_2 , we computed the frequency spectral of κ_p and κ_c at 300 K as shown in the upper panel of Figure 3a. We find that the phonons located at low-frequency region ($\omega < 2.5$ THz) mainly behave as particle-like propagation (see Figure 3a) with highest κ_p approaching to 1.1 W mK^{-1} while the κ_c almost can be neglected. While at mid- and high-frequency region, the κ_c are comparable to κ_p as seen in the middle panel of Figure 3a. More interestingly, we observed that there exists a sig-

nificant increase of the wave-like thermal conductivity contribution (κ_c/κ_1 reaches highest value to 40%) at the mid-frequency region. A further analysis of the projected phonon density of states (p-DOS) reveals that the mid-frequency phonons predominantly originate from the vibrations of Mg_1 atoms as seen in the bottom of Figure 3a, indicating that Mg_1 atoms play a critical role in enhancing the proportion of wave-like contribution. Furthermore, we note that the mean square displacements (MSD) of Mg_1 atoms are larger than that of Mg_2 and Bi atoms, and the discrepancy becomes larger with increasing temperatures (Figure 3b). A larger MSD of Mg_1 atoms in general leads to weaker restriction from around environment, which is consistent with the previous observation of smaller COHP in Mg_1 -Bi bond. In addition, we find that the phonon vibrational mode with mid-frequency of 3.62 THz is dominated by Mg_1 atoms (see the inset of Figure 3b), further indicating that Mg_1 atoms play an imperative role of contributing to anharmonicity. The weak force restriction of Mg_1 atoms in Mg_3Bi_2 generally results in strong anharmonicity and thus enhancing the coherence coupling between phonons. In a short summary, although the κ_p dominates the κ_1 , the κ_c still cannot be ignored especially at high-frequency region, and the weakly bound Mg_1 plays a key role in the wave-like contribution.

Correspondingly, we computed a mode-resolved dimensionless ratio of $R = \frac{\kappa_p - \kappa_c}{\kappa_p + \kappa_c}$ [23] displayed on the phonon dispersion (see Figure 3c) at 300 K to quantify the dominance of phonon transport mechanisms. A value of $R = 1$ indicates the thermal conductivity contribution arising exclusively via particle-like propagation (κ_p), as visualized by the green markers in Figure 3(c). Conversely, $R = -1$ indicates purely wave-like tunneling (κ_c) contributions to thermal transport, represented by the blue markers in the same figure. This bipartite classification rigorously distinguishes between particle-like propagation and coherent phonon dynamics at the mode-resolved level. In details, phonons located at low-frequency region ($\omega < 2.5$ THz) mainly contribute to κ_p (see Figure 3c), which is in line with the frequency-dependent phonon lifetime shown in Figure 2c. In particular, we note that

Figure 3. a, top panel) Frequency spectral thermal conductivity of κ_p and κ_c , (middle panel) the frequency-dependent contribution of κ_c to κ_1 (κ_c/κ_1), and (bottom panel) the atomic projected phonon density of states (p-DOS) of Mg_3Bi_2 at 300 K. b) Calculated temperature-dependent atomic mean square displacements (MSD) of Mg_1 , Mg_2 , and Bi atoms, respectively. The inset is the corresponding phonon vibrational mode with a frequency of 3.62 THz. c) Calculated phonon dispersion of Mg_3Bi_2 at 300 K. The size of circles indicates the contribution to total κ_1 . The blue, pink, and grey indicate the particle-like phonon propagation, wave-like phonon tunneling and coexisting particle-like phonon propagation and wave-like phonon tunneling, respectively.

the phonons along the high-symmetry direction of Γ -M in the first Brillouin zone (see Figure 3c)) make more contribution to the wave-like κ_c than other high-symmetry paths. Along Γ -M, we observed that the flat transverse acoustic phonons (TA1) exhibit small phonon group velocity (see Figure S3b, Supporting Information) and strong anharmonicity (large Grüneisen parameters as shown in Figure S3a, Supporting Information). Therefore, these TA1 phonons have relatively small MFP (shorter than the average bonding length), which is the origin of contribution to κ_c even though its order of magnitude is relative small compared to κ_p . While at high-frequency region, the phonons along Γ -M also give a more significant wave-like tunneling contributions to κ_c than other high-symmetry path, as shown in Figure 3c. Importantly, we note that Mg_1 atoms prefer to vibrate along the in-plane direction according to the molecular dynamics trajectory (see Figure S4, Supporting Information), which correspond to the phonon vibration along the Γ -M direction (corresponding to the in-plane direction of the lattice structure). Therefore, the significant κ_c along the Γ -M is mainly originated from Mg_1 atoms.

2.4. High-Order Anharmonic Effects on Particle-Like and Wave-Like Thermal Conductivity

Returning to Figure 1c, the 4ph scattering has a substantial influence on the κ_1 of Mg_3Bi_2 . Interestingly, we find that κ_p undergoes a dramatic suppression while κ_c exhibits a minor increase after including 4ph scatterings, which are quantitatively evaluated by comparing the accumulative κ_p as shown in Figure 4a,d. Since the suppression of κ_p is more significant than the enhancement of κ_c after including 4ph scatterings, therefore, the collective effects give a reduction of κ_1 . In particular, we observed that the κ_p

at 300 K reduces from 1.62 to 0.90 W mK^{-1} , corresponding to relative reductions of 44.44%, by further considering the 4ph scatterings. This is because the 4ph scattering rates were larger than the 3ph scattering rates, especially in the low-frequency range, as shown in Figure 4b. The mode-resolved Grüneisen parameters (see Figure 4c) simultaneously demonstrate that the Mg_3Bi_2 exhibits a feature of strong anharmonicity. However, we find that the 4ph scattering has negligible effects by comparing the accumulative κ_c (increases from 0.14 to 0.16 W mK^{-1} after including 4ph scatterings) at 300 K as shown in Figure 4d. The magnitude of coherence tunneling terms associated with pairs of phonon branches reveal a minor increase in κ_c with further inclusion of 4ph interactions (Figure 4e,f), indicating that 4ph has weak impacts on wave-like thermal transport in Mg_3Bi_2 . Therefore, we concluded that the 4ph scattering has a more pronounced effect on κ_p than κ_c .

In addition, we note that the κ shows strong anisotropy along the in-plane and out-of-plane directions as shown in Figure 5, which is consistent with its layered crystallographic structure (see Figure 1a). Due to the presence of weak interlayer ionic bonds, the κ_1 of out-of-plane is lower than that of in-plane. Taking 300 K as an example, after considering temperature-induced phonon renormalization, higher-order scattering, and wave-like contributions, the κ_1 of out-of-plane (0.72 W mK^{-1}) is 41.79% lower than that of in-plane (1.24 W mK^{-1}). Furthermore, we find that the κ_c/κ_1 along the out-of-plane increases more significantly than that along the in-plane direction with increasing temperature as shown in Figure S5a (Supporting Information), indicating the superior coherence sensitivity of out-of-plane phonon modes to thermal excitation. Figure S5b (Supporting Information) demonstrate that the density states of κ_c characterized by the coupled phonon modes are significantly enhanced by thermal excitation

Figure 4. a) Cumulative κ_p averaged by the crystallographic directions at 300 K. b) Comparison of 3ph and 4ph scatterings at 300 K. c) Mode-by-mode Grüneisen parameters at 300 K. d) Same as (a) but for κ_c . e) Contour plots of the coherences' part (off-diagonal terms, κ_c at 300 K) associated with various pairs of phonon frequencies (ω_s and $\omega_{s'}$) from 3ph scatterings. f) Same as (e) but for 3+4ph scatterings.

(increased temperature). The temperature-dependent analysis reveals a remarkable enhancement in optical branch coherence, which correlates well with the thermal excitation-induced flattening and proximity effects observed in Figure 1e (Supporting Information). This geometric evolution of the phonon spectrum under thermal activation creates favorable conditions for enhanced interbranch phonon interactions. As a result, with the temperature increasing, the gradually increasing κ_c occupies an increasingly larger proportion. Moreover, we noted that both the in-plane and out-of-plane κ_1 exhibits a weak temperature-dependence trend and they deviate from the classical T^{-1} . This

is mainly due to the competition trend with increasing temperature between κ_p (decreasing with T) and κ_c (increasing with T) as well as the considerable magnitude order of κ_c compared to κ_p , as shown in Figure 5.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, we comprehensively investigate the anomalous thermal transport behavior of Mg_3Bi_2 , using an advanced ab initio simulations with integrating a unified heat transport

Figure 5. Temperature-dependent κ_p , κ_c , and κ_1 along the a) in-plane and b) out-of-plane direction.

theory accounting for particle-like propagation and wave-like coherent transport, phonon renormalization, and fourth-order anharmonic phonon scattering, as well as an in-house experimental measurement. Our predictions agree well with the experimental data, both in terms of the temperature-dependent trend and the order of magnitude of κ_1 . We find that 4ph scattering significantly suppresses the particle-like contribution while enhancing the coherent wave-like contribution with increasing temperature, resulting in a weak overall temperature dependence. The significant anharmonicity and appreciable phonon coherence are primarily attributed to the weakly bonded Mg₁ atoms. This work systematically elucidates the microscopic origins of both the low κ_1 and its anomalous thermal resilience in Mg₃Bi₂, while establishing the central role of Mg1 anharmonicity in sustaining coherent phonon transport. The developed framework, which integrates temperature-renormalization and high-order phonon scattering with wave–particle dual-channel transport, offers a refined strategy for rationally engineering thermal transport in promising TE materials, as quantified by the coherence metric.

4. Experimental Section

Synthesis: High-purity Magnesium turnings (Mg, 99.9%; aladdin) and bismuth shots (Bi, 99.999%; aladdin) were weighed according to the nominal stoichiometry of Mg₃Bi₂ in an Ar-filled glovebox with an oxygen and water level below 0.1 ppm. The raw materials were loaded into a stainless-steel ball-milling jar and ball-milled for 5 h in a high-energy mill (SPEX 8000D, Metuchen, NJ, United States). The ball-milled powders of the samples were collected and transferred into graphite dies with an inner diameter of 10 mm. Immediately, the graphite dies with the loaded powder were sintered by Spark Plasma Sintering system (SPS-222H, Fuji Electronic Industry Co. Ltd) at 1023 K for 3 min under an axial stress of 50 MPa.

Theoretical Methods: All DFT calculations were performed by using the projector-augmented-wave (PAW) technique as implemented in the Vienna Ab Initio Simulation Package (VASP) code.^[26–28] The exchange–correlation energy was described by the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional.^[29] The interatomic force constants at ground 0 K (G-IFCs) were computed with ShengBTE.^[30,31] The temperature-dependent interatomic force constants (T-IFCs) were extracted with the TDEP package.^[32] κ_p and κ_c were computed using the Phono3py package^[33] for 3ph scattering. An in-house Phono3py extension^[24,34] was used to include 4ph scatterings. The crystal orbital Hamiltonian population (COHP) gave the energy contributions for a selected bond calculated with the LOBSTER software.^[35–38] Additional details can be found in the Supporting Information.

The unified treatment of κ_1 in Mg₃Bi₂ included the particle-like and wavelike-like transport. $\kappa_1^{\alpha\beta}$ comprised particle-like ($\kappa_p^{\alpha\beta}$) and wave-like ($\kappa_c^{\alpha\beta}$) terms^[23,39] ($\kappa_1^{\alpha\beta} = \kappa_p^{\alpha\beta} + \kappa_c^{\alpha\beta}$), where α and β are indexing the Cartesian directions. Consider the phonon mode indexed by wave vector \mathbf{q} and branch s . The particle-like contribution, resulted from the diagonal ($s = s'$) terms of the Wigner heat-flux operator,^[23] writes

$$\kappa_p^{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{VN_q} \sum_{qs} C_q^s \nu_{q,\alpha}^s \nu_{q,\beta}^s \tau_q^s \quad (1)$$

The heat carried through the coupling of vibrational modes, described by off-diagonal ($s \neq s'$) terms, writes

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_c^{\alpha\beta} = & \frac{\hbar^2}{k_B T^2 VN_q} \sum_q \sum_{s \neq s'} \frac{\omega_q^s + \omega_q^{s'}}{2} \nu_{q,\alpha}^s \nu_{q,\beta}^{s'} \\ & \times \frac{\omega_q^s n_q^s (n_q^s + 1) + \omega_q^{s'} n_q^{s'} (n_q^{s'} + 1)}{4(\omega_q^s - \omega_q^{s'})^2 + (\Gamma_q^s + \Gamma_q^{s'})^2} \times (\Gamma_q^s + \Gamma_q^{s'}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where \hbar , k_B , V , and N_q are the reduced Plank constant, the Boltzmann constant, the volume of the unit cell, and the number of sampled phonon wave vectors in Brillouin zone, respectively. C_q^s , $\nu_{q,\alpha}^s$, τ_q^s , ω_q^s , $\nu_{q,\alpha}^{s'}$, Γ_q^s ($\tau_q^s = 1/\Gamma_q^s$) are the heat capacity, group velocity, lifetime, phonon frequency, velocity operator, and scattering rate of a phonon mode, respectively. $n_q^s = [\exp(\hbar\omega_q^s / (k_B T)) - 1]^{-1}$ is the equilibrium Bose–Einstein distribution. The underlying wave mechanisms described by the “coherences” term κ_c is phonon inter-band tunneling between any two propagating modes s and s' with the same \mathbf{q} . When the frequencies of the two modes ω_q^s and $\omega_q^{s'}$ are closer, the wave coherence ($\sim c / (\omega_q^s - \omega_q^{s'})$, where c is the speed of sound) increases, resulting in stronger tunneling.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15465176>, reference number 0.

Keywords

atomic bonding, low lattice thermal conductivity, phonon renormalization, wave-like propagation, weakly temperature dependence

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